

Synthesis, Structure and Properties of Bimetallic Manganese(II,III) and Dioxouranium(VI) Complexes derived from Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)oxaloyldihydrazone

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The bimetallic manganese(II,III) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes $[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh}_2)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_4[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]_2[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{K}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{Mn}_3(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ have been synthesized from bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)oxaloyldihydrazone (napoxlh_4). The complexes have been characterized by physical and spectral data. Ir spectral data indicate that the dihydrazone coordinates to the metal centres in keto as well as enol forms in the anti-cis-configuration in all of these complexes.

The dihydrazones derived from condensation of *o*-hydroxyaromatic aldehydes and ketones with organic acid hydrazides are potential polynucleating ligands possessing amide, azomethine and phenol functions¹, which offer varying bonding possibilities in metal complexes because of their multidentate character and can offer any set of donor atoms depending upon the preferred stereochemical disposition of the metal valences and the nature of the bonds formed in the coordination process. Manganese is a biologically relevant metal ion as it has been found to be involved in a wide variety of biological processes². In such systems manganese has been reported to be present in bi- or polynuclear forms. In addition, heterobimetallic complexes of manganese have potential for multi-electron reduction of dioxygen³. Further, the heterobimetallic complexes of dioxouranium(VI) in which the first row transition metal ions⁴ are another constituent exhibit well-behaved four-electron transfer process, a process which occurs in the reduction of dioxygen. Moreover, heterobimetallic complexes derived from widely divergent transition metal ions and innertransition metal ions have potential for activation of small molecules bound to the electron-rich metal centre by the electron-deficient metal centre. A survey of literature has disclosed that while metal complexes derived from simple hydrazones have been studied in some greater details¹, those derived from dihydrazones have received scant attention only^{1,5-8}. Moreover, the corresponding study on their heterobimetallic complexes is virtually absent.

In view of the above importance of the bi- or polynuclear manganese complexes and heterobimetallic complexes of manganese and dioxouranium(VI) and absence of detailed investigation of metal-dihydrazone complexes derived from dihydrazones containing bulky fragments in their molecular skeleton, the present paper reports the synthesis of bimetallic manganese(II,III) and dioxouranium(VI) complexes derived from bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)oxaloyldihydrazone (napoxlh_4).

Results and Discussion

On the basis of various physicochemical studies, the complexes isolated in the present study are suggested to have the formulae $[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh}_2)_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1), $[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2), $\text{K}_4[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3), $[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]_2[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) and $\text{K}_4[\text{UO}_2\text{Mn}_3(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (5) (Table 1). All of the complexes are coloured reddish brown to brownish red. They are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Complexes 1, 2 and 4 showed weight-loss corresponding to four water molecules at 110° while complex 3 showed weight-loss corresponding to two water molecules only. On the other hand, complexes 2, 3 and 5 showed weight-loss corresponding to eight, two and two water molecules at 180°, while complexes 1 and 4 did not show any weight-loss at this temperature. The water molecules lost at 110° indicates that they are part of the lattice of the complexes while those lost at 180° suggest that they are coordinated to the metal centre. Complex 2 was found to have molecular weight equal to (1625 ± 80) in DMSO solution suggesting its dimeric structure. However, slightly higher experimental values for the complex than that expected on the basis of suggested dimeric formulation indicate, most probably, the displacement of water molecules from coordination sphere by DMSO molecules.

Complexes 1 and 2 have molar conductance values 7.8 and $1.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating that they are non-electrolyte⁹. On the other hand, the value for complex 4 is $20.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, whereas that for complexes 3 and 5

are 56.7 and 65.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. In view of the dimeric nature of these complexes in the light of molecular weight determination, we propose that both the cationic species in complex **4** are inside the space enclosed by the anionic coordination sphere, whereas in complexes **3** and **5**, the two potassium ions are inside and the other two are outside the anionic coordination sphere¹⁰.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.)					
	Mn	K	U	F	N	Ligand
1	16.31	8.35	61.30		8.35	61.30
	(15.99)	—	—	—	(8.14)	(61.63)
2	17.00	—	—	—	8.45	65.65
	(17.19)	—	—	—	(8.75)	(65.94)
3	15.37	11.30	—	8.36	8.15	60.35
	(15.65)	(11.09)	—	(8.11)	(7.97)	(60.03)
4	11.00	—	23.37	—	5.24	40.79
	(10.70)	—	(23.15)	—	(5.45)	(41.05)
5	10.16	9.53	15.16	6.99	7.36	53.44
	(10.41)	(9.98)	(15.01)	(7.19)	(7.07)	(53.24)

The determination of the oxidation state of manganese chemically in complexes **3** and **5** by the addition of the complexes to an acidic Fe^{II} solution and back-titration with dichromate, suggests that two manganese centres are oxidized from +2 to +3 oxidation state consistent with their suggested formulation.

Complexes **1** and **2** have μ_{eff} values 7.98 and 8.20 B.M. in the solid state per empirical formula indicating that the manganese atoms are weakly coupled¹¹. A low μ_{eff} value for complex **1** as compared to **2** is inherent in the bridging nature of the acetato group. The same holds true for the μ_{eff} value for the complex **4** (6.25 B.M.). A decrease in μ_{eff} value in case of complex **3** (7.25 B.M.) as compared to those of complexes **1** and **2** may be considered, in view of the absence of other factors, to be indicative of the oxidation of the two metal centres. However, it is less than the value for a spin system consisting of nine electrons suggesting that the Mn^{II} and Mn^{III} centres are coupled to one another. The same holds true for the complex **5** (5.08 B.M.) also.

The ligand shows bands at 374 and 380 nm in the solid state. Complexes **1–4** show strong absorption bands in the region 400–500 nm with fine structure, which arise from charge transfer from ligand to metal. These may have contribution from bands arising from metal-metal interactions as well¹⁶. Any *d-d* band occurring in this region is masked by strong charge transfer bands. Complexes **3** and **5** show one or two bands in the region 500–650 nm which are assigned to *d-d* transitions¹².

The powder esr spectra of complexes **1, 3, 4** and **5** at RT and LNT, show isotropic spectra with signal in the region $g \cong 2$. The hyperfine structure is resolved on the spectrum of complex **1**. This structure consists of a group of 11 lines superimposed on each of the peaks, an observation similar to those of Mathur *et al.*¹³. Each peak is char-

acterized by an average hyperfine splitting of *ca* 43 G and a distribution of peak intensities expected for two coupled spins $I = 5/2$ nuclei, as in the case for ^{55}Mn (1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 5 : 6 : 5 : 4 : 3 : 2 : 1). The hyperfine coupling constant of 43 G is half that of a typical Mn^{II} coupling found in monomeric complexes and is characteristic for a pair of exchange coupled Mn^{II} ions. In DMSO solution as well, isotropic spectra are observed for complex **3** as against resolved spectra for complexes **1, 4** and **5**. Such esr spectral feature in complex **3** may be related to the oxidation of $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ system to $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}$ system, which further indicates that a kind of cooperative interaction exists between Mn^{II} and Mn^{III} metal centres in this complex¹⁴. On the other hand, the esr spectra of complex **5** in DMSO solution at LNT is different from those of complexes **1** and **4** as well as that of complex **3**. The signal in the region $g \cong 2$ shows a hyperfine structure with very strong intensity in the low field region as compared to that in the high field region. Such esr spectral features of this complex may be related to the presence of one Mn^{II} centre in combination with UO_2^{2+} centre and the second Mn^{II} centre in combination with Mn^{III} centre in the same structural unit of the complex.

In the free ligand, strong ir bands were found at 1655 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and 1616 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{N}$). Further, the strong broad bands observed at 3500–3300 and 3382, 3332 and 3278 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{OH}} + \nu_{\text{NH}}$ vibrations. The ν_{NH} bands appeared at higher frequency in complex **1** while the $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ band remained almost at the same position with reduced intensity indicating coordination of carbonyl oxygen atom to the metal centre. The feature of the bands in the region 3550–3000 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of coordinated and lattice water molecules in the complex. On the other hand, in the remaining complexes, the ν_{NH} and amide-I bands are not observed, indicating collapse of amide structure of the dihydrazone. Strong to very strong bands are observed at 1617–1590 cm^{-1} in all of the complexes as against a single band at 1616 cm^{-1} in the free dihydrazone assigned to either $\text{C}=\text{N}$ or $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}$ group¹⁵. The average negative shift of these bands by $\sim 8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests coordination of dihydrazone through $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group to the metal centre. All of the complexes show two very strong bands at 1580–1535 cm^{-1} . While the band at 1578–1555 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (phenolic) characteristic of its involvement in oxo-bridging¹⁵, the band at $\sim 1532 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to ν_{NCO^-} of newly created NCO^- group⁸. The presence of oxo-bridging is also indicated from the presence of weak intensity band at 861–850 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{M}$ grouping¹⁶.

The non-ligand bands occurring in the regions 590–550 and 484–430 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ (phenolic) and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ (carbonyl)¹⁵ respectively. Complex **4** shows a strong new band at 1417 cm^{-1} , assigned to symmetric stretching vibrations of coordinated acetato group¹⁷. However, this band is masked by strong ligand band at 1426 cm^{-1} in complex **1**.

The $\nu_{as}(\text{OCO})$ stretching vibration of coordinated acetato groups appears at 1537 cm^{-1} as a very strong band in complex **1**, whereas it appears merged with ν_{NCO} band in complex **4**. The position of the $\nu_{as}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{OCO})$ bands is characteristic of the presence of bridging bidentately coordinated acetato group¹⁷. The strong bands observed at 517 and 500 cm^{-1} of complexes **3** and **5** are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mn}^{3+}-\text{F}}$ ¹⁹ whereas the strong bands at 430 and 421 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mn}^{2+}-\text{F}}$ ¹⁹. Complexes **4** and **5** show a new strong band at 911 and 892 cm^{-1} respectively assigned to $\nu_3(\text{UO}_2^{2+})$ vibrations of linear uranyl groups.

The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band appears as a set of two bands in the complexes indicating coordination of dihydrazone to the metal centres in the anti-*cis*-configuration which introduces steric crowding in the molecules. As a result, the molecule is bent in such a manner that one-half hydrazone part is out-of-plane of the molecule occupying axial position while the other half remains in the equatorial plane²⁰. This accounts for the splitting of the $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibration of the azomethine group.

On the basis of various physicochemical studies and ir spectral evidences, the dihydrazone is proposed to coordinate to the metal centres in the complexes in anti-*cis*-configuration in keto and enol forms respectively. The structural unit in these complexes is proposed to consist of two dihydrazone molecules in anti-*cis*-configuration holding four metal ions out of which two are present in N_2O_2 coordination chamber while the other two in O_2O_2 coordination chamber. It is suggested that all of them have distorted octahedral stereochemistry around manganese centres present in N_2O_2 and O_2O_2 coordination chambers. The uranyl group inside the anionic coordination sphere is eight-coordinated in complex **5** whereas it is six-coordinated inside the cationic coordination sphere in complex **4**.

Experimental

Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate, uranyl acetate dihydrate, diethyloxalate, hydrazine hydrate, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde potassium fluoride and potassium acetate were of A.R. grade (B.D.H. or E. Merck). Oxaloyldihydrazine was prepared by reacting diethyloxalate (1 mol) with hydrazine hydrate (2 mol). Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)oxaloyldihydrazone was prepared by refluxing hot dilute ethanolic solution of oxaloyldihydrazine (1 mol) with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (2 mol). The yellow precipitate obtained was crystallized from ethanol and dried in hot air-oven ($\sim 70^\circ$), m.p. $> 300^\circ$ (Found : C, 68.00; H, 4.25; N, 3.32. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 67.71; H, 4.23; N, 13.15).

Manganese, uranium and potassium were determined by standard methods²¹. Fluoride was determined as lead chlorofluoride. Dihydrazone ligand was determined volumetrically in $5\text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Nitrogen was determined microanalytically. Water was determined by heating the samples in an oven at $\sim 110^\circ$ and $\sim 180^\circ$ respectively, and

passing the vapour through a trap containing anhydrous copper sulphate which turned blue and estimating the weight-loss. The molecular weight of the complexes were determined in DMSO solution by freezing point depression method. The molar conductance of the complexes (10^{-3} M in DMSO) was measured on a Direct Reading Conductivity-meter with a dip-type conductivity cell. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a DMR-21 spectrophotometer and esr spectra at X-band frequency on a Varian E-112 X/Q band spectrometer using DPPH as an internal field marker. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Faraday method at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant.

$[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) : To an ethanol solution of manganese(II) acetate (1.21 g, 40 ml), a slurry of napoxlhH₄ in ethanol (1.0 g, 38 ml) was added slowly and stirred over a hot-plate using magnetic stirrer at $\sim 70^\circ$ for ~ 10 min. Immediately color of the solution changed from yellow to brown. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h and filtered in hot condition. The resulting brown solid was washed with hot ethanol and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

$[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**2**) : To a hot dihydrazone solution (100 mmol, 30 ml) in ethanol, manganese(II) acetate (200 mmol, 31 ml) solution in ethanol was added dropwise with gentle stirring at ~ 50 – 60° . The resulting brownish red solution was refluxed for 3 h. The reddish brown precipitate obtained was filtered in hot condition, washed with hot ethanol and again suspended in ethanol (50 ml). To this suspension, CH_3COOK (400 mmol, 125 ml) solution in ethanol was added and refluxed for another 3 h. The orange-brown precipitate so obtained was filtered hot, washed with hot water-ethanol mixture, ethanol, benzene and finally with ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

$[\text{UO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]_2[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**4**) : To an ethanolic suspension of complex **1** (1.0 g, 40 ml), uranyl acetate dihydrate solution in ethanol (1.35 g, 50 ml) was added maintaining the molar ratio at 1 : 2 and stirred over a hot-plate for 10 min at 70 – 75° . The color of the solution gradually changed from brown to brownish red. The resulting solution was refluxed for ~ 6 h and then filtered hot. The resulting brown solid was washed with hot ethanol, benzene and finally with ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The filtrate from the above reaction mixture was concentrated by evaporation. The solution so obtained yielded a solid which was filtered in cold condition, washed with hot ethanol, ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . It was found to be identical with the above precipitate.

$\text{K}_4[\text{Mn}_4(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**3**) and $\text{K}_4[\text{UO}_2]\text{Mn}_3(\text{napoxlh})_2\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ (**5**) : These were prepared by following the same general procedure. A typical procedure is as follows. To an ethanolic suspension of complex **1** (1.5 g, 50 ml), an aqueous solution of KF (1.08 g, 10 ml) was

added and stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 70–75° for ~2 h. The color of the solution gradually changed from reddish brown to deep brown color. The complex was filtered hot and washed with hot water-ethanol mixture, ethanol, benzene and finally with ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Decomposition temperature of all the complexes (yields 82–95%) was found to be > 300°.

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